

MEDICAL SCIENCES

3D SKIN BIOEQUIVALENT

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of studies on the development of a bioequivalent skin (dermis) based on autologous cells deposited on biodegradable microspheres. The 3D tissue-engineering design under development is intended for the pathogenetic treatment of severe skin lesions by filling in the deficit of the organ cell mass in the affected area, as well as stimulating tissue regeneration processes in patients with trophic ulcers in diabetes mellitus, pressure sores and other skin diseases.

Keywords: skin bioequivalent, mesenchymal multipotent stromal cells, fibroblasts, skin diseases, trophic ulcers.

Introduction

One of the most severe complications of diabetes mellitus is diabetic foot syndrome (DFS). According to some authors, DFS is the main cause of lower limb amputation and reaches about 50-70% [1]. About 13 thousand operations are performed annually in Russia due to this disease. Also, at least 1.5 million people suffer from skin diseases such as trophic ulcers, autoimmune (epidermolysis bullosa, complicated forms of psoriasis, collagenosis), thermal burns. The developed skin equivalent will reduce the number of amputations in diabetes mellitus and other diseases accompanied by severe skin damage. Also, the use of a skin equivalent will significantly speed up the processes of regeneration of skin lesions, which will reduce the percentage of disability and, accordingly, disability.

The aim of the study is to develop a bioequivalent of the skin based on the patient's autologous cells deposited on biodegradable microspheres, and intended to replace damaged cells, as well as to stimulate the processes of skin tissue regeneration.

Materials and methods

We used cultures of MMSCs and cultures of fibroblasts isolated from three patients aged 24 to 42 years after they signed a voluntary informed consent. MMSCs were isolated enzymatically from adipose tissue obtained as a result of lipoaspiration in the region of the lower horizontal fold of the anterior abdominal wall. Isolation of cell culture of fibroblasts was carried out from a skin flap. The flap was obtained from a healthy donor. Explantation of the flap was performed from the gluteal region. Next, the skin explant was placed in a shipping solution containing specialized antibiotics for in vitro use. The resulting primary culture was incubated under standard conditions (37°C, CO₂

5%, humidity 95%). For cultivation, a Ham's / DMEM F-12 mixed culture medium (Sigma Aldrich), fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Sigma Aldrich) at a concentration of 10%, and vascular endothelial growth factor VEGFA were used. All cultures involved in the experiment have been tested for the study of genetic [2] and infectious safety [3, 4]. The number of MMSCs in cultures was assessed by the method of indirect immunofluorescence by the presence of the Stro-1 marker [5], which is specific for cells with pluripotency properties. Typically, fibroblast cultures contain up to 0.05% Stro-1 positive cells [6].

To develop the optimal mode of enrichment of fibroblast cultures with multipotent mesenchymal stem cells, a number of experiments were carried out:

Fibroblast cultures were mixed with MMSC cultures in the ratio:

- 25% MMSC and 75% fibroblasts;
- 50% MMSC and 50% fibroblasts;
- 75% MMSC and 25% fibroblasts.

In all three variants, 2 mixing modes were used:

1) cells were removed from the culture surface with trypsin-EDTA (Sigma), the enzyme was neutralized with fetal calf serum (Sigma), washed in PBS solution 2 times. Then the washed cultures were mixed by pipetting and centrifuged at 150 G for 5 minutes;

2) cells were removed from the culture surface with trypsin-EDTA (Sigma), the enzyme was neutralized with fetal calf serum (Sigma), washed in PBS solution 2 times. Then the washed cultures were mixed by pipetting and centrifuged in DMEM solution (Sigma) at 100 G for 15 minutes.

The cells obtained in the pellet were seeded on the culture surface in DMEM and DMEM / Ham F-12 media, supplemented with 5% FBS (Sigma), at 37 ° C, 5% CO₂ concentration and 95% humidity.

A scaffold containing poly (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan structured using electromagnetic radiation with a wavelength of 400 nm to 200 nm was chosen for the application of cell cultures.

5 products were tested:

- Product No. 1 of a microsphere of structured poly- (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan and a mixed culture of fibroblast cells and MMSC No. 12MK 3204681

- Product No. 2 of a microsphere of structured poly- (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan and a mixed culture of fibroblast cells and MMSC No. 12MK 3204682

- Product No. 3 microspheres of structured poly- (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan and mixed culture of fibroblast cells and MMSC No. 12MK 3204683

- Product No. 4 of a microsphere of structured poly- (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan and a mixed culture of fibroblast cells and MMSC No. 12MK 3204684

- Product No. 5 of a microsphere of structured poly- (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan and a mixed culture of fibroblast cells and MMSC No. 12MK 3204685

The cell culture was applied to the scaffold (microspheres) by the following methods:

1) application of the cell culture to the scaffold immediately before use - the cell suspension was mixed with previously prepared microspheres in a 1: 1 ratio and applied to the wound surface;

2) application of a cell culture to a scaffold followed by culturing a tissue-engineered construct for a day - the cell culture was adhered to prepared microspheres and placed in a CO₂ incubator for 24 hours (37°C, 5% CO₂, 95% humidity);

3) separate cultivation of cell culture and scaffold, followed by application of cells to microspheres - microspheres were placed in a bottle with a culture medium, the bottle was placed in a CO₂ incubator for 24 hours, the cell culture was cultured in a separate bottle. Cell adhesion to microspheres occurred immediately before application to the wound surface.

Results and discussion.

According to the results of the experiment, it was revealed that a milder centrifugation mode and subsequent cultivation in complete medium (DMEM) promotes the greatest preservation of cellular elements with multipotency properties (table 1).

Table 1.

The proportion of Stro-1 positive cells (%) in culture depending on the mixing mode and the initial amount of MMSC on the 7th day of cultivation

Mixing mode and composition of the culture medium	25% MMSC and 75% fibroblasts	50% MMSC and 50% fibroblasts	75% MMSC and 25% fibroblasts
Mix mode 1 DMEM / Ham F-12	0,35	0,4	0,4
Mix mode 1 DMEM	0,37	0,4	0,4
Mix mode 2 DMEM / Ham F-12	0,45	0,5	0,5
Mix mode 2 DMEM	0,55	0,55	0,57

The shortest time to reach a monolayer is observed in cultures initially mixed in a proportion of 50% MMSC and 50% fibroblasts, as well as 75% MMSC and 25% fibroblasts, when cultured in DMEM medium and the 2nd mixing mode. In a culture initially containing 25% MMSC, the time to reach 90% of the monolayer is one day longer. At the same time, the proportion of Stro-1 positive cells in all three cases differs slightly.

Due to the fact that the isolation and cultivation of MMSC takes much more time than the isolation and cultivation of fibroblasts, and also taking into account the specifics of diabetes mellitus (DM1), which limits the volume of the patient's adipose tissue explant, the optimal mode of obtaining and cultivating a mixed culture of MMSC and fibroblasts can be considered as follows:

Cultures are mixed in a ratio of 25% MMSC and 75% fibroblasts by centrifugation at 100 G in DMEM medium, with a culture seeding density after mixing not more than 20% confluence.

The cells are cultured in DMEM medium supplemented with 5% FBS at 95% humidity and 5% CO₂.

According to the results of the studies, the optimal composition of microspheres was isolated - microspheres of structured poly- (2-acetamido-2-deoxy-D-glucosyl) -D-glucuronoglycan No. 12MK 3204684. Microspheres of this composition provide the greatest adhesion of cells to their surface.

As the optimal method for applying cell culture to the scaffold, method No. 3 was chosen - with pre-cultivation of the scaffold and cell culture, since this method allows to achieve the desired consistency of the tissue-engineered structure (the consistency of a thick ointment allows filling the irregularities of the wound defect, the viscosity of the product ensures fixation in the wound and protects the product from flowing out).

Conclusions.

1. As a result of the experiments, the most acceptable composition of the scaffold was selected, on which the cell cultures were adhered, and the optimal mode of cultivation of MMSC and fibroblasts was also created.

2. For the treatment of severe skin injuries with a complicated relief of the wound surface, a 3D bioequivalent of the skin has been developed in the form of a gel, which allows a wound defect of any complexity.

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3D CARTILAGE CONSTRUCT FROM MULTIPOTENT MESENCHYMAL STROMAL CELLS

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Abstract

Damage to the cartilage surface of the joints is a common pathology. Conventional drug therapies are effective only at the initial stage of the disease and only slow down the further development of the disease. In subsequent stages, it is necessary to apply surgical methods from replacing a defect to complete prosthetics of a damaged joint.

In order to replace defects in cartilage tissue, a three-dimensional bioequivalent was created based on autologous multipotent mesenchymal stromal cells.

Keywords: osteoarthritis, cell therapy, multipotent mesenchymal stromal cells, three-dimensional bioequivalent.

Introduction

Osteoarthritis (synonyms: deforming osteoarthritis, arthrosis, deforming arthrosis) is a degenerative joint disease caused by damage to the cartilage of the articular surfaces.

A large-scale study conducted in Russia revealed manifest (accompanied by clinical symptoms) osteoarthritis in 64.3% of those examined over 15 years of age [1].

The first place in pharmacotherapy is occupied by non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs prescribed to relieve pain and inflammation. In the phase of acute pain, when osteoarthritis can be complicated by synovitis, in-

tra-articular administration of corticosteroids (diprospan, triamcinolone, and hydrocortisone) is used to relieve pain and inflammation [2]. Chondroprotectors (chondroitin sulfate and glucosamine) are still used as a course of treatment orally, intramuscularly, intraarticular in the first and second stages of the disease. Hyaluronic acid preparations are also used for intraarticular administration. However, the results of modern scientific studies show the lack of effect of these drugs compared with placebo [3]. A network meta-analysis of 10 major clinical trials conducted in 3803 patients with OA of the knee and hip joints failed to reveal any clinically significant effect of glucosamines, chondroitin sulfates or a combination of these in reducing joint pain